

Main model comparison on SPARC/Rotmod

Model	Mean MSE	Median MSE	Mean RMSE	Comment
Baryonic Newtonian	2883.08	1799.80	45.65	Baryons only
RAR/MOND benchmark	444.52	193.53	17.17	External acceleration-relation benchmark
Harmonic FLOW-CM	397.82	140.94	16.19	Final nodal-conductance law